

Anthropomorphic Metaphorical Models with the Concept of “Love” in English and Uzbek

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Article information:

Manuscript received: 04 Sep 2024; **Accepted:** 04 Oct 2024; **Published:** 11 Nov 2024

Abstract: This article aims to explore the anthropomorphic metaphorical models associated with the concept of 'love' in Uzbek, examining their linguistic nature and cultural significance. Linguistic structures and anthropomorphic metaphors in expressions of love are analyzed, and the role of language in the formation of human emotions is discussed.

Keywords: Cognitive model, metaphor, anthropomorphic metaphorical model.

INTRODUCTION.

The concept of 'love' is a fundamental aspect of human experience that transcends cultural boundaries, yet its expression often varies significantly across different languages. In the Uzbek language, love is not merely a feeling but is frequently articulated through anthropomorphic metaphors, which attribute human characteristics to abstract concepts. One of the effective methods for studying concepts is metaphorical modeling. In cognitive linguistics, scholars emphasize that natural language fills cognitive gaps through cognitive models. “A cognitive model can be considered a fundamental mechanism that ensures the processing and storage of information about the world in human consciousness” [4,45].

MAIN PART. This analysis focused on identifying common metaphors that embody love as a personified entity, exploring their meanings, contexts, and underlying cultural values. The study also considered how these metaphors reflect the emotional depth and complexities embedded in the expression of love within Uzbek society.

Researchers say that cognitive metaphor is one of the leading ways of modeling the conceptual world view. According to V.I. Postovalova, metaphor plays the role of a prism through which a person understands and explains himself and the world around him.[6,57]

There are many terms for designating metaphorical models that figuratively represent one or another denotative (conceptual) sphere. To designate such modeling, linguists use the terms «archetype» or «metaphorical archetype» (Panchenko, Smirnov), «conceptual metaphor», «basic metaphor» (Lakoff, Johnson), «mental model» (Johnson-Laird), «metaphorical model» (Baranov, Karaulov), «model of regular polysemy» (Shmelev; Chudinov), «metaphorical modeling» (Kravtsova), etc. All these terms have a different internal form that emphasizes the linguistic, general philological, psychological or cognitive aspects of the phenomenon under consideration, reflect the traditions of various scientific schools.[2, 164–169]

J.Lakoff and M.Johnson, who studied metaphor through a cognitive-linguistic approach in

their work “Metaphors We Live By,” acknowledge that metaphor encompasses not only our everyday lives and language but also our thoughts and actions. They emphasize that the essence of metaphor is understanding and experiencing one thing in terms of another.[3,5]

Scientists have also classified various types of metaphorical models based on the relationship between source and target domains, with ontological metaphors playing a significant role among them. These metaphors identify human experience with objects or substances. A clear example of an ontological metaphor is personification, where non-human entities are attributed human characteristics. The unique aspect of personification lies in the fact that different human traits are utilized in each specific instance of metaphorization. Therefore, personification serves as a broad category that encompasses a diverse array of metaphors, each rooted in particular human attributes. [3, 49–60]

One of the examples provided by Lakoff and Johnson for conceptual metaphor is “Love is a journey”, which makes it easier to understand and experience love through the lens of JOURNEY. In the phrase “We went our separate ways”, the conceptual domain understood as “love is a journey” is expressed metaphorically, where “love” serves as the target domain and “journey” represents the source domain. Thus, the metaphorical expression “they went separate ways” conveys the idea that for two people who embark on the journey of love, their individual travels equate to “going their own ways”, meaning that they have ended their relationship. Lakoff and Johnson emphasize that some concepts are constructed almost entirely through metaphor, illustrating that the concept of “love” is primarily structured metaphorically: “*love is a journey, love is a physical force (electromagnetic, gravitational, etc.), love is a patient, love is madness, love is magic, love is war*” [3,85].

A.P. Chudinov gives the following definition of a metaphorical model: «A metaphorical model is an existing and emerging in the mind of a native speaker of a connection scheme between conceptual spheres, which can be represented by a certain formula «X is Y» [1, 70]. It can be understood that the schematic representation of the relationship between conceptual domains existing and emerging in the minds of speakers of a particular language is expressed as a metaphorical model.

The modeling of the “Love” concept in the linguistic picture of the world involves identifying the methods of expressing the concept and reconstructing its integral structure. In the Uzbek language, anthropomorphic, physiological, naturmorphic, zoomorphic, phytomorphic, and abiomorphic (object-related) metaphorical models that express the concept of “love” have been identified. This article will focus on anthropomorphic metaphorical models.

According to anthropomorphism, inanimate objects are attributed with the ability to perform actions (such as living, dying, experiencing emotions, etc.). In the early stages of societal development, anthropomorphism was used to explain incomprehensible phenomena of nature and the laws of the universe and has been one of the most significant manifestations of the metaphorical nature of thought since ancient times.

“An anthropomorphic metaphor is a metaphor that arises from the transfer of human characteristics to things, objects, and also to other species beyond humans” [5, 182]. Within the framework of the anthropomorphic metaphorical model, the feeling of “love” is compared to a living organism.

RESULTS. The research highlights several key anthropomorphic metaphors related to the concept of ‘love’ in the Uzbek language. This metaphorical model is realized through the metaphors LOVE – PERSON and LOVE – OPPONENT.

LOVE – PERSON:

1) Love can be born, live, die, and be buried like a human or any living organism. In the

Uzbek language contexts, this emotional experience manifests as a human undergoing this biological process, as can be seen in the following examples:

Hayotdan alamzada yurak ko'zlari yovuzlik pardasida to'silgan, muhabbat o'tlig' pokiza fazilat bunday biqiq va qorong'i bo'shliqda yashay olmas edi. (Tohir Malik, "Shaytanat"); Biroq, birinchi muhabbatini tuproqqa ko'mgan Azizxon kechagi Azizxon emasdi. (Said Ahmad, "Ufq")

2. Love can appear as a human and have physical imperfections, for example, it can be blind:

Muhabbatning ko'zi ko'r deydilar! Qismat degani shu: oldingdan oqadi – qadrlamaysan... Kaftingda turadi – ko'rmaysan, o'z qo'ling bilan tashlab yuborasan... (O'ktam Usmonov, "Girdob")

3. Love may have the ability to feel like a human. The following example portrays love that has fallen into despair:

Ikkala yosh ko'ngil qorong'i muhitning og'ir kishanlariga bog'langan holda noumid muhabbat bilan bir-birlarining hasratida entikar ekan...(Abdulhamid Cho'lpon. "Kecha va kunduz")

4. Love demonstrates actions characteristic of humans, particularly abilities and functions such as crying, sleeping, and waking up:

Sekin-asta ortimga tisarilib sizdan uzoqlashar ekanman, nigohingizda menga atalgan muhabbat yig'layotganini ko'rdim. Biroq ovutishga haqqim yo'q. (Go'zaloy Solih qizi, "Siz o'shami");

Shu jumladan muhabbat ham mangu. Faqat uning makoni – toza dil. U kirlangan qalblarga qiyo boqmaydi, nodonlar ko'nglini tark etadi. (Abdumutal Abdullayev, "Alushta ertagi")

Qo'shni sinfda o'qiydigan oltinsoch qiz uning o'smirlik yuragida muhabbat deb atalmish tuyg'uni uyg'otganida hali onasiga nisbatan nafrati to'lib toshmagandi. (Tohir Malik, "Shaytanat 4-kitob")

The metaphorical expression of the feeling of "love" through human-like behaviors can also be observed in Uzbek proverbs. For example, "Muhabbat boylikka boqmas", "Muhabbat ketsa, nafrat kelar", "Muhabbatning ko'zi – ko'r", "Oltin zanglamas, sevgi qarimas", "Sevgining ko'zi ayb ko'rmas", "Sevgi qarimas, asl chirimas", "Qalbg'a qarimoq yo'q, Sevgiga – o'lim".

In these proverbs, expressions such as "boqmas", "ketsa", "ko'zi – ko'r", "qarimas", "ko'zi ayb ko'rmas" exemplify the anthropomorphic metaphor of expressing love through human actions or traits.

In the metaphorical model LOVE – OPPONENT, love manifests as an opponent in battle. This metaphor is based on a person's struggle with love as if it were an adversary, and it can be expressed with the following verbs: *g'olib kelmoq, erishmoq, vayron qilmoq, zabt etmoq, ezib tashlamoq, qiynamoq, bo'g'moq, asir qilmoq, qul bo'lmoq, jang qilmoq, olishmoq.*

Love can triumph or be defeated in the struggle: *Mahkamning izzati nafsni Ochilnikichalik tegmanozik emas edi, ayniqsa hozir, u muhabbatda g'olib kelgan bir paytda ojiz ko'rinishdan qo'rqmas, kuchi yetmayotgan narsalarni ochiq ayta olardi. (Pirimqul Qodirov, "Uch ildiz")*

Shuning uchun hozir Zamirani ko'rishni jon-u dili bilan istasa ham, uning oldiga borishi mumkinligini bilsa ham aksini qilardi, muhabbatini irodasiga bo'ysundirishga urinib, o'zi bilan o'zi tinmay olishardi. (Pirimqul Qodirov, "Uch ildiz")

Love can capture a person and make them a slave, while in turn, a person can also exert force against it.

To'g'ri, muhabbatga qul bo'lmaslik kerak. Lekin uni buncha ichga qamab, istasam yo'qotib yuboraman deyish ham to'g'ri emas. (Pirimqul Qodirov, "Uch ildiz")

U javobsiz muhabbatga qarshi birdan bir chora — qizni unutish, o'zining sevgi hislarini bo'g'ish deb bilardi. (Pirimqul Qodirov, "Uch ildiz")

CONCLUSION. The exploration of anthropomorphic metaphorical models of the concept of 'love' in the Uzbek language illustrates how language can shape and reflect cultural perceptions of emotions. These metaphors not only enhance the richness of linguistic expression but also provide insight into the values, beliefs, and practices surrounding love in Uzbek society. Future research could examine comparative aspects with other languages to highlight the universality and uniqueness of love expressions across cultures, further enriching our understanding of this profound human experience.

REFERENCES

1. Chudinov A.P. A Cognitive Study of Political Metaphor (1991 – 2000): Monograph. Ural. state ped. un-t. Yekaterinburg, 2001. 238 p.
2. Kamenieva I. Semantic and cognitive approaches to the analysis of metaphorical models. *Modern Engineering and Innovative Technologies*, 3(25-03), 2023.
3. Lakoff G. and Johnson M. *Metaphors We Live By*. – Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 1980.
4. Маслова В. А. Когнитивная лингвистика. – Минск: ТетраСистемс, 2004.
5. Махмараймова Ш.Т. Hozirgi o'zbek tili. Leksikologiya. – Toshkent: "Firdavs-Shoh nashriyoti", 2021.
6. Постовалова В.И. Картина мира в жизнедеятельности человека. Роль человеческого фактора в языке: Язык и картина мира / отв. ред. Б. А. Серебренников. М.: Наука, 1988.
7. Fayzullaevna T. M. Comparative analysis of phraseological units of the concept "love" in the English and Uzbek languages // *Berlin studies transnational journal of science and humanities*. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 1.6 Philological sciences.